

THE ROLE OF THE CONCEPT OF TEACHING AND LEARNING THE SUBJECT OF "EDUCATION" IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of the "concept" of teaching and learning the science of "education" in the education of the young generation. educational methods of the teacher that increase the quality of education in teaching the science of education are considered.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, concept, student, science, process, value.*

Today's processes of globalization, scientific and technical progress, innovation the needs of society create many opportunities for young people. They are making quick decisions, forming innovative thinking, to national and universal values while increasing intellectual potential is setting vital demands of being faithful. Therefore, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, continuous education is a state science current in the implementation of policy in the field of education directed to solving problems. Science is a new work in the education of the young generation priority tasks aimed at bringing to the stage, the main goal and determines directions.

The science of education is general at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was introduced in secondary educational institutions starting from the 2020-2021 academic year. This science "National to inculcate the idea of "from recovery to national progress", prepare them for a socially successful life, active citizenship position, responsibility, commitment, legal awareness and culture, deep worldview, healthy faith, with the aim of forming qualities such as enlightenment and tolerance put In creating the concept of science and textbooks, Japan, Singapore, England, From the experience of foreign countries such as UAE, China, Korea, Russia, Germany was used. Education because the educational process is an extremely complex process effectiveness depends on the activity of the pedagogue and student, the availability of educational tools, depends on the organizational, scientific, methodical perfection of the educational process

The educational process includes two interrelated activities - the teacher and the student. In the process of education, the mind of the student is formed, feelings and various abilities are developed, ideological, moral, volitional, aesthetic characteristics are formed, a system of scientific views on nature and society is formed, physical strength is strengthened. The student in the process of education moral qualification that meets the moral requirements of the society and habits are formed. To achieve this, the student's mind (education in the process), to his feelings (in class and in various extracurricular activities), to his will (in the process of organizing activities, controlling behavior) with a systematic and regular influence. In the process of education, any of these (consciousness, emotions, will) are neglected if left, it becomes difficult to achieve the goal.

The essence and tasks of the educational process aimed at a certain goal planned and organized by the teacher:

- In order to form or lose which characteristic of the student will be planned;

- Looking for sources that serve to educate or lose these feelings;

Theoretical and practical resources that serve the purpose which and where it is planned to be used. Nowadays, interactive methods and information technologies are used in the educational process the interest in using it in the educational process is increasing day by day. Such one of the reasons for this is that until now students in traditional education have only if they are taught to acquire ready knowledge, from modern technologies and to use it, to search for the knowledge they are acquiring on their own, independently learning and thinking, analyzing, even drawing final conclusions by themselves teaches to release. The teacher in this process is personal development, formation, knowledge creates conditions for receiving and education, and at the same time management, acts as a guide. There are "Brainstorming" "Brainstorming", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "BBB", "Fifth plus", "6x6x6", "Discussion", "Role-playing game", FSMU, "In small groups work", "Rounded snow", "Zigzag", "I will say the last word" modern technologies are used in education today.

Thus, the above general process of education in the education system laws are manifested in the following objective and strictly repeated relations: teaching its purpose is determined by its content; teaching method that corresponds to the purpose and content and methods are chosen; and the effectiveness of teaching is checked by the positive results achieved in teaching. the quality of educational knowledge is measured by the level of maturity of students. Training in the teacher education system to direct education to a specific pedagogical goal clearly defining the purpose of teaching the science, the tasks of the educational science that formed its basis should get However, with the general goal of teaching the science of education, the science of education it is not enough to know the tasks. At the same time, in the implementation of general tasks the role and tasks of the educational science course taught in each class, in turn, this course in the implementation of the tasks of the educational science of teaching, each of its departments, departments topics, and even partial tasks of each lesson. Because each educational science lesson is part of the general education system of the entire educational science course has a place, it is a kind of general task set before teaching the science of education in this lesson element or part is solved.

Activation of students' cognitive activity in the effective teaching of education plays an important role. Pupils' cognitive activity is active in class and extracurricular activities. It depends on many factors, first of all, the ideological and scientific-theoretical aspects of the training content. to be at a high level, to be able to reveal the most important thing in a lively and convincing way, and this students' understanding of the importance of studying the events in depth and in them. It depends on arousing enthusiasm for learning. In this place, the teacher trains students his control over the mastering of the content, his ability to manage the students' learning, as well as from their existing knowledge and skills to master their new knowledge it is also important to be able to use it, that is, to update the acquired knowledge and acquired skills is important.

The science of education is very rich and diverse in content. Education science teaching and students. Through learning activities, it affects their consciousness, upbringing and thinking, their maturity helps to find. So, the content of the training is to teach the science of education in the educational system it is also important to increase the quality and efficiency and to activate the cognitive activity of students serves as a factor. Therefore, it has a positive effect on the activation of the teacher's cognitive activity in choosing methodical methods and tools that ensure the effectiveness of education in general it should also include the content of the educational material being studied.

Today, the interest and attention to increase the efficiency of education by using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process is increasing day by day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students find the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and analyze it, and draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates the conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual and the team. In such an educational process, the student becomes the main figure. Today, the main reason why special attention is paid to the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is the following:

1. First of all, in the scope of the possibility of implementing personality-developing education in pedagogical technologies, special attention is paid to the issue of implementation of developmental education in the Law on Education.

2. Secondly, pedagogical technologies provide an opportunity to widely introduce a systematic activity approach to the educational process.

3. Thirdly, pedagogical technology encourages the teacher to pre-design the technological chain, starting with the goals of the educational process, and ending with the creation of a diagnostic system and control of this process.

4. Fourthly, since pedagogical technology is based on the use of new tools and information methods, their application

To sum up, the content of educational work in our country at the present time is aimed at forming a well-rounded generation. Necessary conditions and opportunities have been created in the republic to raise a healthy and mature generation, to bring up the young generation as fully developed individuals who fully meet the requirements of the 21st century. Documents, programs and plans of state significance have been developed for specific, purposeful implementation of work in this regard. It is enough to mention that the adoption of the "Law on Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" is aimed at high general and professional culture, raising a competent generation capable of solving promising tasks.

Education is an activity aimed at bringing the young generation to adulthood, forming social consciousness and behavior in it, and is aimed at forming mental, physical, moral, and spiritual qualities of a person, in order to ensure that a person lives in society. are the processes of finding the content of the necessary features.

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